

Case Study

Title: Role of Media and Communication in Social and Cultural Change in Nepal

Abstract:

This case study examines the transformative impact of technology, media, and communication advancements on Nepali society and culture in the 20th century. With the advent of social media, widespread internet access, and mobile technology, traditional communication norms have evolved significantly. These changes have influenced social interactions, cultural practices, and even religious ceremonies in Nepal. The study highlights both positive outcomes, such as enhanced cultural visibility and connectivity, and challenges, including misinformation and diminished face-to-face interactions. By promoting digital literacy and ethical online behavior, Nepal can navigate these challenges and leverage technological advancements to preserve its cultural heritage. The findings suggest that a collaborative effort between government, educational institutions, and communities is essential for fostering inclusive growth and maintaining cultural identity in the digital age. This study, based on limited observations, calls for further research to provide a comprehensive understanding of these dynamics.

Keywords:

Technology, Social Media, Nepali Society, Cultural Change, Digital Literacy, Communication, Globalization, Media Impact, Cultural Heritage, Misinformation, Digital Inclusion, Technological Advancements

Objectives:

In the 20th century with modernization and globalization worldwide, the changes or the ripple effect of technology and social media on society and communities cannot be ignored. The study of social and cultural change is significant in understanding, predicting, and analyzing where the current world, country, community, and cultural practices stand. In this case study, we will briefly discuss the findings and summarize how technology innovations, media, availability of communication, and access to IT resources have affected Nepali Society and culture—also some possible solutions, and predictions of society's growth.

Introduction:

In the 20th century, when modernization and globalization began to spread, new technologies changed the way people communicate all around the world. Nepal was no exception. With the rise of technology, social media, and easier access to information, Nepali society and culture went through some big changes. This case study looks at how media and communication have influenced Nepali society and culture. We'll explore how technology, digital media, and communication have transformed Nepal. By looking at what we've found, we hope to understand how technology is affecting Nepal and what we can do about it.

Findings:

In the context of Nepal, back in the days when there was no or very little access to social media like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and other internet access, the typical conversation between the people living in a typical Nepali society was not the same as today. At this time people in society gossip about the videos, viral news, and information they watched,

listened or found on social media. Even the late 70s and 80s generation of Nepalese from the old generation are affected and most likely to gossip and chat on the content of social media.

The younger generation of mothers or modern mothers themselves create a personal social media account for their kids and children. They Post videos, reels, and images of their child like my child's birthday, my child's first day at school, and even more.

There was a practice or tradition of having a digital photo frame of a newborn child in a home kept by a parent as a memo. But now due to the availability of mobile, newly born child pictures can be instantly captured, uploaded, and shared publicly on the internet.

During and after the COVID-19 duration social media apps like Messenger, Viber, and WhatsApp are widely used to perform small to big Hindu religious events like Puja, Bhaitika, and Dashain Tika and even take blessings from senior citizens, relatives, and parents.

An app like Hamropatro provides services like Jyotish, Kundalini, online horoscope, and personal meetings with Jyotish (astrology information) which shows how Hindu cultural practices are being digitalized by technology.

At the young and teen-age foreign culture, fashion, celebrity, and lifestyles have brought huge impact. Korean dramas, Japanese anime, and Western lifestyles like having coffee, burgers, pizza, etc. Recently in Nepal, a new trend is going out, hiking, trekking, and other adventures.

From radio to mobile device transformation, in the back 3 decades having a radio and television was a sign of luxury but now everyone even older generation people have access and are using the mobile that shows how our cattle rearing, shepherd generation transited from the radio to mobile.

There were few national media NTVs, such as Kantipur TV where people solely relied upon their news but now there are various types of content and news on social media bad content that directly negatively and indirectly affect people's thinking, perspectives, and actions, and false information make people more confused and brings ambiguity in the past People in the village used to gather in the evening to watch the news, movies, and TV shows at the TV owner's house. Now this trend is no longer valid.

There are very few Postal services in Nepal which were the most important as it was only the medium in the past to receive and send messages or letters.

There was a time when people had no access to tech and did not have enough leisure time to chit chat, share stories, and talk, and the kids used to play more outdoor games now the people residing even in the same room may not have proper and open-ended conversation, and the people have not enough time for anybody else to have a free talk and open-ended conversations like in the past. This shows our friendly culture and open conversations are slowly depicted, and the people are becoming more independent and carefree.

But there are some positive effects like our cultural events, festivals, and dress are shared, visualized, and promoted via social media. Newari Communities celebrate Bisket, Indra Jatra, and Kirati celebrating [Udauli](#), the Hindu Festival Mahashivaratri, the Muslim festival Eid, and all other ethnicities.

With the mobile application, religious and holy books are digitalized, and anyone can carry them everywhere at any time instead of heavy and bulk religious text. The citation and elaboration of holy text can be listened to through a mobile app.

Discussion:

The findings underscore the profound impact of technology and media on Nepali society and culture. Social media platforms have revolutionized communication, altered conversational norms, and enabled widespread sharing of information. However, concerns regarding misinformation and shifts in traditional communication patterns have arisen.

To address these challenges, promoting digital literacy and critical thinking skills is crucial. Educating individuals, especially the youth, on how to discern credible information from misinformation can mitigate the negative effects of social media. Additionally, fostering a culture of responsible online behavior and ethical content sharing can help preserve cultural values amidst technological advancements.

Looking ahead, Nepal is poised to experience further societal and cultural changes as technology continues to evolve. Embracing these changes while safeguarding cultural heritage will require a collaborative effort between government, educational institutions, and communities. By fostering digital inclusion and promoting cultural awareness, Nepal can navigate the complexities of the digital age while preserving its rich cultural identity.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the rapid evolution of media and communication technologies has profoundly influenced the social and cultural dynamics of Nepali society. From the emergence of social media platforms to the widespread adoption of mobile devices, technology has reshaped the way individuals interact, communicate, and engage with cultural practices. While the digital age has brought about both positive and negative changes, including increased connectivity and cultural exchange, it has also posed challenges such as misinformation and the digital divide. Moving forward, Nepali society must

adapt to the digital landscape while preserving its cultural heritage and values. By harnessing the potential of technology for social good and promoting digital literacy, Nepal can navigate the complexities of the digital age and foster inclusive growth and development.

The case study is mostly structured from the limited observation, reflection/changes, and image of the current society so the case study may not be 100% perfect and complete. It may require more in-depth study and revision.

References:

1. Rai, Dilli Hang. (2024). Role of Media and Communication in Social and Cultural Change in Nepal.